

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue VIII, August 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

@pinagpalapublishing

pinagpala_publishing

www.pinagpalapublishing.com

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.327-329 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The Power of Positive Work Atmosphere

BEBECHE D. PAGALAN, LPT

Teacher

Himaya Elementary School

El Salvador City, Misamis Oriental, X, Philippines

LEONITA C. SUMALINOG, RL, MLIS

Librarian

Xavier University- Ateneo de Cagayan

Cagayan de Oro City, Misamis Oriental, X, Philippines

It is crucial to establish a positive and pleasant work atmosphere in order to improve employee morale and efficiency. An inclusive and welcoming work environment includes various important factors such as encouragement, chances for development, security, equity, passion, and helpful criticism. Every one of these factors is crucial in creating an atmosphere that makes employees feel valued, inspired, and involved. Understanding the importance of these factors enables us to grasp their influence on both personal achievement and the organizations' overall prosperity.

Establishing clear and open communication channels is crucial for fostering a positive work environment according to Schaufeli & Bakker (2024). When workers are motivated to openly express their thoughts, address issues, and give helpful criticism, the trust and respect within the team increase. This active communication enhances employee recognition and engagement, leading to a significant enhancement in their overall job contentment and joy (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2024). Organizations can prioritize these traits to create a positive work environment that enhances employee wellness and effectiveness.

Workers in a firm that holds frequent brainstorming sessions are able to offer distinctive answers to assignments or obstacles. When these proposals are welcomed with genuine enthusiasm and support from team leaders and coworkers, morale improves and people are motivated to continue sharing their ideas (Amabile, 2024). Employees feel more confident and appreciated when they receive favorable feedback. Furthermore, when team leaders and coworkers recognize and cherish these concepts, they set a good example for the whole team. This demonstrates the recognition of all contributions and promotes a culture of communication and teamwork. Therefore, team members are more prone to feeling included and motivated, leading to a boost in overall engagement and productivity according to Edmondson (2024).

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blessed M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.327-329 International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Workers in educational institutions and libraries require adequate tools and resources for achieving success. For example, when a library implements a new computer system for book management, providing comprehensive training and ongoing assistance assists staff members in overcoming initial problems, enhancing their confidence and efficiency (Eisenberger et al., 2024). Similarly, excellent training for new online learning tools allows teachers to adjust rapidly, increasing work satisfaction and teaching performance (Eisenberger et al., 2024). Furthermore, mentorship programs in libraries, where experienced librarians train newer staff, and similar initiatives in schools, where seasoned instructors encourage newcomers, considerably contribute to professional development and job dedication (Allen et al., 2024). These supportive measures are vital for fostering a positive work environment and improving overall performance and satisfaction.

Recognizing and rewarding success is important in every workplace, including libraries. For example, when a library team successfully completes a large project or improves their services, celebrating the achievement with a small celebration or recognizing staff members' efforts may be immensely motivating. Such award not only emphasizes the team's work, but it also maintains an appreciation and excellence culture. By publicly acknowledging these accomplishments, the library develops a pleasant environment in which staff feel valued and driven to keep working at their peak. This strategy is consistent with studies that highlights the importance of recognition and awards in maintaining employee motivation and satisfaction (Cameron & Quinn, 2024).

Providing safety and inclusivity in schools and libraries is also important in creating a pleasant and supportive atmosphere in which all persons feel respected and cherished. Safety is proactively addressing and managing concerns such as discrimination, harassment, and unfair treatment in order to provide an environment in which everyone can work or learn without fear of unwanted consequences. To effectively address issues, this requires developing clear policies, offering training, and keeping open lines of communication. In contrast, inclusiveness emphasizes the necessity of creating an environment in which everyone feels truly welcome and respected. This is actively working to include different perspectives, celebrating diversity, and ensuring that everyone has equal opportunities to participate and contribute. Together, these initiatives contribute to a pleasant environment that fosters respect, belonging, and a feeling of community among both staff and clients.

Maintaining a good attitude is essential, especially during difficult times. Optimism entails actively finding solutions rather than focusing solely on problems, which can dramatically enhance the confidence of the employee. Having a positive work environment in libraries and educational institutions greatly benefits both individual employees and the organization as a whole. When workers operate in a positive and inviting atmosphere, their productivity increases while they experience higher job satisfaction and reduced stress levels. This favorable environment frequently results in fewer absenteeism and increased employee retention. Furthermore, it develops team ties, increases collaboration, and fosters a strong feeling of community. Focusing on solutions is an important part of maintaining a happy workplace. For example, if a library faces a large loss in budget, leadership may hold problem-solving sessions to investigate new funding sources or change programs. This proactive strategy keeps staff engaged and focused on solving obstacles, thereby preserving a pleasant environment and assisting the library's attempts to traverse challenging times (Seligman, 2024). Creating a healthy work environment in libraries and schools offers long-term benefits that contribute to continued success and growth. When organizations prioritize making their

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue VIII (August 2024), p.327-329 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

workplaces friendly and engaging, they frequently see major benefits such as greater innovation, staff retention, and overall performance. Investing in a healthy work environment benefits libraries and schools by creating a location where staff are driven to flourish, resulting in improved performance and long-term organizational success (Cameron & Quinn, 2024).

Finally, creating a positive work atmosphere is very essential for the success of libraries and schools. These institutions foster a culture of support, growth, safety, inclusivity, optimism, and constructive criticism, allowing employees to feel appreciated, engaged, and motivated. This investment not only increases job satisfaction, but it also boosts productivity and develops a high-performance team. Libraries and schools that prioritize these characteristics see better results and longer-term organizational growth (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13624056

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.